

ҚОРАҚАЛПОҒИСТОНДА
ФАН ВА ТАЪЛИМ

ҚАРАҚАЛПАҚСТАНДА
ИЛИМ ҲӘМ ТӘЛИМ

НАУКА И ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ
В КАРАКАЛПАКСТАНЕ

SCIENCE AND EDUCATION
IN KARAKALPAKSTAN

3/2-сон
Нукус
2025 й.
ISSN 2181-9203

Khojamuratova R.T., Jangabaev D.M., Almatbayev N.K. Use of distance zonding and geoinformation systems for monitoring the impact of collector drainage waters on soil conditions and agriculture in the Republic of Karakalpakstan.....	190
Kosnazarov K.A., Kosnazarov K.K., Omarav A.K. The issue of cultivating forest plants with collector-drainage water in the southern Aral sea region...	196
Artikova G.N., Meldebekova S.U., Djumanazarova Z.K., Yodgorova N.U. Macroelemental composition of certain organs of <i>Elaeagnus angustifolia</i> L., growing in territories with a high level of salinity.....	201
Juginisov T.I., Adenbaeva A., Sapparbayev A.S. Bioecological features of Anocothermes termites in the conditions of Karakalpakstan.....	207
Genjemuratov A.S. Influence of soil moisture on the growth and development of cotton under different irrigation.....	210
Artikova G.N., Yodgorova N.U., Ahmadjanova G.O., Tañirbergenov B. Determination of the free amino acid composition of the fruit of the plant elaeagnus Angustifolia L.....	214
TECHNICAL SCIENCES	
Askarov M.A. Electrophysical properties of the silicon solar cell with nanoheterojunctions based on lead chalcogenides.....	222
Niyazova Z.M. Development of a local territorial planning strategy for the western-north city of Karakalpakstan based on green infrastructure.....	228
Kurbonov N.N., Khoshimov F.A., Uzaqbaev Q.A. Root causes and classification of technical failures in large-scale wind power plants: analysis and prevention strategies.....	234
Rakhmonov I.U., Jalilova D.A., Najimova A. Selection of a mathematical modeling method for voltage regulation in spinning mills.....	239
Nazarov Z.S., Buriyev Sh.U., Avazov A.N. Scientific basis for the application of various support methods in capital and preparatory mine workings at great depths.....	243
Svaykosov S.O. Types of catalysts of the hydroisomerization process and their comparative advantages and disadvantages.....	250
Razzakov S.J., Berdakov D.E. Modeling of connections of bending elements of wooden structures.....	253
Uzakov T.Dj., Isakova D.M. Safety of hydrotechnical installations and environmental protection.....	258
Niyazova Sh.M. Kainar andesite porphyrite a valuable raw material for basalt fiber production.....	262
Yunusov B.X., Dadaboev Q.Q., Kurbanbaeva M.Sh. Justification of the principal diagram of a heat exchange device used in a cooling tower module of a thermal power plant.....	268
Nazarov N.I., Fayziyev J.B., Nazarov S.I., Mirzoyeva G.A. Physicochemical analysis of a bimetallic phthalocyanine complex bound to a tetrapyrrole ring.....	272
Safarov A., Kudenov I., Gayipov I. Mathematical model of magnetic field distribution in magnetic conduct of wide range current transformer.....	277
Sottiqulov E.S., Jalilov A.T., Karimov M.U., Abdazov D.K. Infrared spectroscopy and gel chromatography methods for studying the structure of newly synthesized NCAN-55 plasticizer.....	281
Uteuliev N., Abdaliev G., Kalmuratov B. Development and application of a grammatical model for the Karakalpak language using artificial intelligence.....	290
Ibadullaev M., Esenbekov A.J., Berdanov T.T., Bazarbaeva A.X. On the methodology for calculating the electromagnetic system of a vibration exciter.....	294
Khudayberdiyev S.A. Cloud technologies and peripheral computing: Key trends of 2024.....	299
Botirov F.B., Haydarov E.D. Analysis and ways to eliminate ransomware malware.....	304
Uteuliev N.U., Orinbaev A.B. Solving the problem of optimizing electricity transmission costs using the interior-point method.....	308
Esenbekov A.J. Research of electromechanical systems with reverse connection.....	313
Gulmirzaeva G.A., Rashidova D.E., Nietbaeva G.B., Reymova L.U. Intelligent data analysis and algorithmic approaches for decision support.....	316
Haydarov E.D. Types of malware in corporate networks and their comparative analysis.....	322
Seytimbetov D.M. The use of iot technologies and optimization systems in managing water flow in hydraulic structures.....	326
Ibadullaev M.M., Esenbekov A.J., Berdanov T.T., Esemuratova T.G. Structural diagram of an electromagnetic vibroauthor with automatic construction to resonance.....	330
Uteuliev N.U., Orinbaev A.B., Madreymova Z.B. Transforming a multi-objective optimization model into a single-objective linear programming form and its application to agricultural problems.....	335
Kalmuratov B.B. Application of polyethylene (HDPE) pipes in thermal power plants: Technological, operational and economic aspects.....	341
Durmanova S.S., Turaev Kh.Kh., Nabiev D.A. Morphological and thermogravimetric analysis of cobalt–calcium containing phthalocyanine pigment...	348
Gulmirzaeva G.A., Rajabov J.A., Nietbaeva G.B. Existing methods for diagnosing melanoma and an artificial intelligence-based diagnostic system.....	354
Kenjayev X.B. Automatic analysis and generalization of text documents based on keyword database.....	359
Kholboeva A.I., Turayev Kh.Kh., Nurqulov F.N., Ishmurodova D.K., Kholiyorova M.K., Karimova N.J., Mavlonova S.A. Efficient synthesis methods and applications of zinc-based organic antiseptics.....	370
Melikuziev M.V., Najimova A.M., Usmonov F.I. Increasing the share of renewable energy sources in urban power supply design.....	376
Paluanov B.A., Pirmatov A. Improvement of the possibility of obtaining high-quality fiber from machine-picked raw cotton.....	383
Djurayeva S.R., Fayziyev J.B. Obtaining red pigment from hibiscus (<i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i>) flowers at low temperature and its physicochemical study.....	387
Kurbanova A.A. Method for producing calcined soda using waste gases in the carbonation process.....	392
Kamalov Kh.U., Khudaybergenov A.R. Comparative analysis of cubic and spherical quantum dots for field-effect transistor modeling with gaas mosfet.....	397
SOCIAL SCIENCES	
Yeshmuratova A.A. Using the “Opposite attitude” method in teaching the subject “Information technologies in technical systems”.....	404
Sultanova R.K. The social pedagogical necessity of developing students' legal competence.....	410
Alauatdinova M.Kh. Prospects of ecotourism development in the Republic of Karakalpakstan.....	414
Ataev J.E. Assessing role of small business in improving population well-being in Uzbekistan.....	420
Ishankulov B.M. Slalom rowing training management.....	425
Dospanova A. Combating excessive dependence on artificial intelligence in education: a creative approach to revitalizing critical and imaginative thinking.....	428
Bayzhanov S.X., Sarsenbaev S.M. Current issues in the development of agricultural economy in the Republic of Karakalpakstan.....	433
Turdimambetov I.R., Dauletbaev O.U. Didactic foundations, principles and criteria of using interactive methods in teaching geography of Karakalpakstan.....	437
Ashurova M. Protection of property rights in housing through proprietary-legal remedies.....	443
Allanazarova B.K. Improving the management of financial stability in insurance companies.....	452
Babanov Sh.A. Neighborhood law - as an institution of civil law.....	458
Abdukhakimov M.T. Land ownership rights, their protection, and the improvement of control mechanisms in land-related relations.....	460
Atamuratova N. Enhancing tourism potential in Karakalpakstan through gis-based ecotourism and cultural heritage planning.....	467
Edenbayev E.I. Tourism industry assortment optimization models and their role in enhancing the competitiveness of industrial enterprises.....	477
Babanov Sh.A. Neighborhood rights and their protection.....	483
Sauxanov J.K., Zarekeev A.A. Exploration and economic advancement of seedless grape production.....	486
Smetov M.I. Formation of theoretical aspects of the organizational and economic mechanism of agriculture.....	491
Zarekeev A.A. Scientific determinants and multifactorial influences on the enhancement of grapevine fertility.....	496
Kurbonova M.B. Methodology for developing creative and proactive leadership skills in students.....	501
Dastamova M.N. Comparative analysis of state policy on preventing violence against children in Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan.....	505
Aytbaev R.X. Social and economic changes in agriculture in the regions of Uzbekistan.....	508
Madaminova M. Shashmaqom – a pearl of the national classical musical art.....	513
Karimova I. The history of creativity in Uzbek compositional art.....	517
Toleпов E.T. Teaching economic subjects in schools based on innovative technologies.....	521
Dusimbetova N.B., Qayimova S.D. Methods of developing transmedia competencies in journalism education.....	524
Muxambaev T.S. "Shaping moral competence in the modern education process: Pedagogical foundations".....	528

**PHYSICOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF A BIMETALLIC PHTHALOCYANINE COMPLEX
BOUND TO A TETRAPYRROLE RING**

¹Nazarov N.I., ²Fayziyev J.B., ³Nazarov S.I., ⁴Mirzoyeva G.A.

¹Academic Lyceum of Bukhara State Medical Institute

²Tashkent Scientific Research Institute of Chemistry and Technology

³Bukhara State University

⁴Academic Lyceum of Bukhara State Technical University

Gmail:nurullo.nazarov.85@list.ru

Summary: *In this article, the physicochemical properties of a bimetallic phthalocyanine complex containing copper and manganese ions were investigated. The molecular structure of the synthesized sample was determined using infrared (IR) spectroscopic analysis, and the absorption regions corresponding to the functional groups in the sample were analyzed. The thermal stability of the complex was studied by thermogravimetric (TGA) and differential thermogravimetric (DTA) methods. Based on the obtained analysis results, it was found that the bimetallic phthalocyanine complex exhibited high thermal stability.*

Key words: *Phthalocyanine, copper chloride, manganese chloride, urea, pigment, catalyst, thermal stability, IR, TGA, DTA*

In recent years, phthalocyanine-based compounds have been widely applied in various branches of industry as organic semiconductors, pigments, catalysts, and gas sensors. The properties of these compounds depend on the nature of the metal atom located at the center of the phthalocyanine, the functionalization of peripheral groups, as well as the formation of additional coordination bonds within the resulting complex. In particular, bimetallic phthalocyanine complexes containing two different metal ions are distinguished by their high thermal stability, strong electron-donating ability, and unique optical and electrical properties. Due to the synergistic interaction between the metal atoms in bimetallic phthalocyanine complexes, their semiconducting, catalytic, and optical sensitivity characteristics differ significantly from those of phthalocyanines based on a single metal. At present, interest in bimetallic phthalocyanine complexes containing two different metal ions is increasing. Compared to monometallic phthalocyanines, these bimetallic complexes exhibit broader functional properties, with their electrical conductivity, optical, and catalytic characteristics demonstrating higher efficiency [1].

Using infrared (IR) spectroscopy, the molecular structure of metal phthalocyanine compounds, the bonding characteristics of the central metal ions, and the vibrations between atoms within the molecule can be determined. Studies have shown that variations in the nature of the metal ion cause noticeable changes in specific regions of the IR spectrum, particularly in the range of 1300–1500 cm⁻¹, which mainly corresponds to the vibrations of C–N, C=C, and C=N bonds, as well as to the deformation vibrations of isoindole and pyrrole rings. In particular, the absorption bands in phthalocyanine structures are highly sensitive to the vibrations of aromatic rings and ligands located close to the central metal [2–3]. During the synthesis of bimetallic phthalocyanines, various combinations of metal ions (for example, Zn–Fe, Mn–Ni) are used, which makes it possible to modify their physicochemical properties according to the intended purpose [4]. The stability and decomposition mechanisms of metal phthalocyanines were studied using thermal analysis (TGA/DTA) methods. In the TGA curves of the obtained complexes, a multi-stage mass loss was observed: in the range up to 200 °C, the release of moisture and low-molecular impurities; around 400 °C, the decomposition of the main ligand framework; and in the range of 400–650 °C and above, the successive decomposition of isoindole rings accompanied by the formation of metal oxides [5]. The thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential thermal analysis (DTA) of the pigment obtained by modification of copper phthalocyanine were also carried out. A detailed study

of the thermogravimetric and differential thermal behavior revealed the thermal stability of the pigment [6].

Materials and methods. Phthalic anhydride, urea, copper(II) chloride, manganese(II) chloride, catalyst, heat-resistant beaker, filter paper, Büchner funnel, vacuum pump, thermometer, heating furnace, drying oven.

Synthesis process. For the synthesis, 4 mol of phthalic anhydride, 4 mol of urea, 0.5 mol each of copper(II) chloride and manganese(II) chloride, and a catalyst were mixed. The resulting mixture was placed in a heat-resistant beaker and heated in a furnace at 220 °C for one hour. As a result, a porous, dark green substance was formed in the vessel. The obtained product was washed several times with distilled water and filtered using a Büchner funnel with the aid of a vacuum pump. Then, it was dried in a drying oven at 100 °C for one hour. The infrared (IR) spectrum of the synthesized bimetallic phthalocyanine containing copper and manganese ions was recorded (Figure 1). The following absorption bands corresponding to the functional groups present in the sample were identified.

Figure 1. IR spectrum of phthalocyanine containing copper and manganese ions

The absorption regions corresponding to the functional groups present in the sample, along with the types of vibrations characteristic of these bonds, are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Absorption region (cm ⁻¹)	Type of vibration	Functional group / Bond description
3194	Stretching vibration	(–N–H) bonds in phthalocyanine
3047	Stretching vibration	(–C–H) bonds of the aromatic ring
1506–1608	Stretching vibration	(–C=C) double bonds within the phthalocyanine ring
1417	Stretching vibration	(–C–N–C–) nitrogen–carbon–nitrogen bonds in the ring
1286–1332	Stretching vibration	(–C–N) bonds in the ring
1165	Deformation vibration	(–C–H) bonds in the ring

1118	Stretching vibration	Coordination bonds (Mn–N) and (Cu–N)
1089	Deformation vibration	Out-of-plane vibration of (–C–N–C–) atoms
1066	Deformation vibration	Ring deformation
948–900	Deformation vibration	(–C–H) bonds, displacement of hydrogen atoms out of the ring plane
873–754	Deformation vibration	(–C–N–C–) bonds in the ring
779	Deformation vibration	(–C–H) bonds in the ring
721	Deformation vibration	(–C–H, C–C–) bonds in the ring
690	Stretching vibration	Central (Cu–N) copper–nitrogen bonds
640	Stretching vibration	Coordination (Mn–N) bonds of manganese atom

From the above analysis results, it can be concluded that the obtained sample indicates the formation of a phthalocyanine complex containing copper and manganese metals.

To determine the thermal stability of the obtained sample, the thermal decomposition stages of the bimetallic phthalocyanine containing copper–manganese ions were investigated using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). The results obtained from this analysis provide information on the decomposition regions, making it possible to determine the thermal stability of the copper–manganese phthalocyanine (Cu–Mn–Pc) complex and its stepwise decomposition behavior. The values of the exothermic and endothermic processes observed during the analysis are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Derivatogram of the bimetallic phthalocyanine containing copper and manganese ions

The TGA curve shown in the derivatogram indicates that three intensive decomposition stages occurred in the analyzed sample.

The first decomposition stage takes place in the range of 30.03 °C–249.40 °C, where the sample mass decreases by 1.305 mg, corresponding to 19.32%. In this stage, the evaporation of adsorbed water formed during the chemical reaction occurs, as well as the decomposition of low-molecular starting materials (such as phthalic anhydride and urea) that did not fully react during the synthesis of phthalocyanine.

The second decomposition stage occurs in the range of 249.40 °C–550.33 °C, where the sample mass decreases by 1.971 mg, corresponding to 29.183%. This stage represents the main decomposition phase of the sample. During this process, the cleavage of the phthalocyanine aromatic ring leads to the thermal degradation of the organic components. At the same time, the metal–ligand (Cu–N, Mn–N) bonds within the complex begin to break, resulting in the decomposition of the structurally complex phthalocyanine molecule. The products released during this stage mainly consist of carbon oxides and nitrogen.

The third decomposition stage takes place in the range of 550.33 °C–801.68 °C, where the sample mass decreases by 1.097 mg, corresponding to 16.24%. In this stage, the remaining organic fragments and carbonaceous residues undergo complete decomposition. The final products of decomposition are the oxides of copper and manganese, which remain as residues. Beyond 801.68 °C, no further mass change is observed, as shown at the end of the TGA curve, indicating the formation of thermally stable residues.

Conclusion. The results obtained by infrared (IR) spectroscopy confirm the formation of the bimetallic phthalocyanine complex synthesized from copper and manganese ions, as evidenced by the observed ring vibrations, coordination bonds between the central metal and nitrogen atoms, aromatic ring stretching and deformation vibrations, and absorption bands corresponding to functional groups. Thermogravimetric analysis of the obtained phthalocyanine complex was carried out, and its thermal stability was determined.

References

1. Kobayashi N. Bimetallic phthalocyanines: synthesis, structure and unique electronic properties // *Coordination Chemistry Reviews*. – 2002. – Vol. 227–228. – P. 129–152.
2. Kulik, L. V., Kuregyan, A. G., & Khimich, T. G. (2007). Correlation dependences in infrared spectra of metal phthalocyanines. *Russian Journal of General Chemistry*, 77(2), 204–208.
3. Kobayashi, N., Ogata, H., Nonaka, N., & Luk'yanets, E. A. (2004). Infrared spectra of phthalocyanine and naphthalocyanine in sandwich-type rare earth complexes. *Journal of Porphyrins and Phthalocyanines*, 8(11), 1290–1299.
4. Gürek A. G., Ahsen V. Synthesis and properties of unsymmetrical bimetallic phthalocyanines // *Journal of Porphyrins and Phthalocyanines*. – 2000. – Vol. 4. – P. 317–326.
5. Seoudi R., Said A.A., El-Bahy G.M. FTIR, TGA and DC electrical conductivity studies of phthalocyanine and its complexes // *Journal of Molecular Structure*. – 2005. – Vol. 753, №1–3. – P. 119–126.
6. Мирзаева Ф.Дж, Тураев Х. Х, Умбаров И.А, Файзиев Ж. Б. Мис фталоцианинини модификациялаш ҳамда уларнинг ик спектри ва термик тахлили // *Eurasian journal of academic research*. Volume 2 Issue 12, November 2022. Page 391-395

Rezyume: Ushbu maqolada tarkibida mis va marganes ionlari saqlagan bimetallic ftalosianin kompleksining fizik-kimyoviy xossalari o'rganildi. Sintez qilingan namunaning molekulyar tuzilishi infraqizil (IQ) spektroskopik tahlil yordamida aniqlanib, namuna tarkibidagi funksional guruhlarga xos yutilish sohalari tahlil qilindi. Olingan namunaning termogravimetrik (TGA) va differensial termogravimetrik (DTA) tahlil usullari orqali kompleksning termik barqarorligi tadqiq qilindi. Olingan tahlil natijalari asosida bimetallic saqlagan ftalosianin kompleksining yuqori termik barqaror xossani namoyon qilganligi aniqlandi.

Резюме: В данной статье изучены физико-химические свойства биметаллического фталоцианинового комплекса, содержащего ионы меди и марганца. Молекулярная структура синтезированного образца была определена методом инфракрасного (ИК)

спектроскопического анализа, проведён анализ областей поглощения, характерных для функциональных групп образца. Термическая стабильность комплекса исследована с использованием термогравиметрического (ТГА) и дифференциального термогравиметрического (ДТА) методов. На основе полученных результатов установлено, что биметаллический фталоцианиновый комплекс проявляет высокую термическую стабильность.

Kalit so‘zlar: Ftalotsianin, mis xlorid, marganes xlorid, karbamid, pigment, katalizator, termik barqarorlik, IQ, TGA, DTA

Ключевые слова: фталоцианин, хлорид меди, хлорид марганца, карбамид, пигмент, катализатор, термическая стабильность, ИК, ТГА, ДТА